

Impact of Smart Classroom Teaching on the Achievement of Students in Mathematics with Respect to Gender

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Abstract

The present study is an experimental one and is conducted in lucknow district of uttar Pradesh .the investigator has taken 79 students of an English medium icse board school of lucknow using simple random sampling technique. The purpose of this research was to know the impact of smart classroom teaching on the achievement of boys and girls. Is their any difference in achievement with respect to mode of teaching and with respect to gender? The data for the study was collected by pre test and post test (an achievement test in mathematics) constructed by the researcher .the findings revealed that smart class is more effective than conventional method of teaching for both boys and girls for gaining in achievement in mathematic subject at junior high school level .findings also revealed that smart class is more effective for boys as compared to girls in improving their achievement in mathematics subject.

Keywords: Smart Class, Teaching of Mathematics, Achievement, Gender. |

Introduction:

Quality education is an essential requisite in today's competitive environment .The traditional approach of lecture and note taking has lost its effectiveness as the modern day around education grow .In effort to grow academically it must be considered that differentiated modalities of teaching and learning are necessary to implement deeper levels of growth and conceptual development .Academic achievement have always been the centre of educational research and despite varied definitions about the aims of education, the academic development of the child continue to be the primary and most important goal of education . What factors promote achievement in students? How far do the different factors contribute towards academic achievement? (Ramaswamy, 1990).Research have indicated the academic achievement of learner is effected by various variables : gender, intelligence ,socio economic status ,methods, techniques of teaching ,teachers ,school facilities ,area etc.therefore child achievement is a combined effect of various variables.

It is unreasonable to expect that spoken or written words alone to convey the volume of relevant information to the learner. This poses a great challenge for teachers and educators, especially in the primary and junior levels, wherein a good study habit and a firm group of basic concept should be developed. *Einstein famously said that his pencil was more intelligent than he was meaning that he could achieve far more using his pencil as an aid to thinking than he could unaided. (Pratima,2013). There is a need to recognize that modern digital technologies like Smart class are the pencils of today .* In smart class, the use of interactive white board allows for subject matter to be presented in a more stimulating and interactive way. Students are shown video clips related to undertaken concept with the help of the technology in digital classrooms, the teaching sessions can also be recorded for further use by uploading the recorded documents in the web. Rather than just sitting and being lectured to, students are able to take more of an active role in their learning with the use of an interactive whiteboard. In a smart classroom enabled schools, the classrooms are connected to the knowledge centre where all the digital contents are linked to the server. Mathematics to most is a complex and difficult subject. The tendency for most students is to consider the subject as one that in boring, thus creating lack of interest in the topics being discussed. Teachers can access the lessons they want to teach during their teaching periods, they can use it to demonstrate; take learners through an audio-visual journey and above all help them to learn better. A teacher has endless possibilities when it comes to infusing this piece of technology into math classroom. School are increasingly adopting digital teaching solutions to make the classroom environment more inclusive and participatory. Role of the teacher cannot be interchanged with the technology, but if the technology allows for better transformation of information, we can

argue that learning should still be improved. Smart technologies claim that they help enable students and teachers by saving time organizing information visually through the manipulation features. Smart class also enables teachers to instantly assess and evaluate the learning achieved by their students in class with an innovative assessment technology- smart assessment system designed by Educomp. In India it was launched by Educomp in 2004. It was conceived and developed around the ideology that for technology to become an integral part of day to day teaching and learning practices in schools, it needs to move right in to the classroom where students and teachers spend over 80% of their teaching learning time.

Review of related literature :

T. JeyaSelvaKumari and Dr. S. P. Denisia, (2013) in their study on “Emerging Technology of Smart Class Teaching for Secondary School Teachers.” stated that the use of emerging technology of smart class teaching is very important both for teachers and students. This technological approach of emerging technology of smart class teaching for secondary school teachers will fulfill the gaps in students’ knowledge, understanding, and application.

Pratibha Sharma (2013) investigated the ‘Role of interactive Multimedia for enhancing students achievement and retention in English at secondary level. She suggested that the interactive Multimedia Method proved to be better than conventional direct method of teaching English to class 7 students.

AnuradhaSekhri (2013) Investigated the ‘Effect of SMART class Instruction on the performance of student’ in Chemistry at Junior high school level and concluded that smart class instruction has significant effect on performance of students in chemistry in 9th class.

Anita menon (2014) investigated on ‘effectiveness of smart classroom teaching on the achievement in chemistry of secondary school students’ The results revealed that students achieved higher when taught in smart classes as compared to conventional mode of instruction.

AnuragChaudhary, GauravAgrawal, MeghnaJharia(2014) stated that this new technology helps the students with the benefit of learning with a different experience. The methods of e-learning make the classroom more interactive and interesting. It has also created a greater impact on our society as well as on education system.

Dr. SavitaSrivastava (2015) worked on “Efficacy of Educomp Smart Class” and revealed that Smart class is a harmonious blend of the modern and the tradition . the multimedia Instructional strategy enhanced the student’s cognitive achievement and also interest in Math’s. The students’ cognitive achievement and interest in math’s were enhanced mostly by the multimedia strategy and minimally by the conventional strategy irrespective of sex.

Importance of the study:

The use of technology in education is increasing day by day. The technological tools like computer, language laboratories overhead projectors are extensively being used to get children better versed with the lesson taught in the classrooms. One of these tool; SMART class technology is getting its hold over schools majorly. This new technology helps the students with the benefits of learning with a different experience. This method make the classroom more interactive and interesting. The smart classes have their own merits and demerits but this new technology is welcomed by the society in a great manner. So the researcher was curious to analyse the impact of SMART class on the achievement of students in mathematics with respect to gender of learner at junior high school level .

Statement of The Problem:

“Impact of smart classroom teaching on the achievement of students with respect to gender.”

Operational Definitions:

SMART Class: Smart Class is a revolutionary classroom technology. It include smart board ,projector, internet, stylus or digital pen and multimedia device .teaching is done through smart board using the smart software as a part of their lesson plan in every classroom period . It makes use of mapped curriculum 2D and 3D digital content which the teacher could access right in the classroom and project it on whiteboard, to elucidate and explain critical concepts, across virtually all subjects.

Conventional class : it is a regular classroom which keeps the teacher in the centre and uses lecture method for teaching the students .the teaching aids is the black board ,charts , etc

Mathematics: Mathematics is the science of numbers, word sign etc which help us to know about magnitude, direction and space.

Achievement : achievement is the indicator of the student’s level of acquired knowledge or skill ,which has been gained as a result of training or experience .In general meaning it is the outcomes . for the purpose of the study achievement is defined in terms of the marks obtained by the students in mathematics achievement test constructed by the researcher **Variable** :Independent variable :teaching methods was taken as independent

variable i.e. smart class method and conventional class method .Dependent variable :achievement of students in mathematics test was taken as the dependent variable .

Objectives of the study:

1. To compare the achievement of girls taught through smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching in mathematics .
2. To compare the achievement of boys taught through smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching in mathematics .
3. To compare the achievement of boys and girls taught through smart classroom teaching in mathematics.

Hypothesis of the study :

1. There is no significant difference between the mathematics achievement of girls taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.
2. There is no significant difference between the mathematics achievement of boys taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.
3. There is no significant difference between the achievement of boys and girls taught through smart classroom teaching.

Delimitations -

1. one English medium school of Lucknow city was taken for the study.
2. Only students of class IX are included in the study.
3. The study is delimited to some topics of mathematics.

Research design : the study was experimental so a true experimental design : pre- test and post- test equivalent group design was used to study the impact of smart classroom teaching with respect to gender .

Research tools :

A self constructed achievement test in mathematics was used as pre –test and post test .it was based on the text book of mathematics of class 9 by M.L. Aggarwal .

Population and sample : the school was selected purposively where smart class was available .79 students of class 9 of an English medium school of lucknow district were selected randomly. the students were selected on the basis of (achievement test)pre test constructed by the researcher .then they were divided into experimental and control group equally .both the groups were made homogenous academically before the treatment .

Procedure : the teaching program for the smart class and conventional class was prepared by the researcher which includes the selection of content ,achievement test and lesson plan as per the syllabus of subject. students of control group were taught by lesson plan prepared by the researcher on the chapters statistics and coordinate geometry. the students of experimental group were taught same chapters of mathematics through smart board using the software **tata class edge** . the nature and requirement of the two classes were kept in mind while preparing the teaching experiment .a pre test was administered before the treatment .then teaching of 4 weeks was given . after the treatment a post test was administered for collection of data.

4. Analysis, Interpretation and Discussion -

Analysis 1.

According to Ho1: There is no significant difference between mathematics achievement of girls taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.Ho1 is interpreted by the mean , standard deviation and t – value.

For the verification of Ho.1. The researcher administered an achievement test in mathematics as pre- test on the girls of experimental group and control group. both the groups girls were academically equal or homogeneous in nature before the experimental treatment was given. The result of the pre test is given in table

1. Pre - TEST mean score of GIRLS of experimental and control group

Table 1

Girls pre test	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference	T.Value	S OR NS
Experimental	9	2.77	0.83	0.11	0.81	NS
Control	9	2.66	1.11			

Df 16 , level of significance at 0.05 =2.12 and LOS at 0.01 =2.92

The table 1 shows ,the ‘t’ value is 0.81 of the pre test scores of girls of experimental and control group. This value is statistically not significant at 0.5 level of significance .

After pretest ,girls of both the groups were given treatment .the experimental group was taught through smart board and control group was taught through conventional method of teaching .after the experiment post test was taken to find the impact of the teaching methods. the mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of girls in post test is given in the table2 .

Post - TEST mean score of GIRLS of experimental and control group

Post test	N	M	Sd	Mean difference	T.Value	S OR NS
Experimental group	9	19.55	3.39	1.55	0.45	NS
Control Group	9	18	5.04			

Result of the analysis 1:

Table no.2 and figure no. 1 show the mean achievement of girls of experimental and control group .the mean values are 19.55 and 18 respectively. The t value is 1.55 between post test scores of girls of experimental and control group, which is statistically not significant at 0.5 level of significance with degree of freedom 16. The graphical representation of the result is given in the figure 1.

The bar graph showing the mean and standard deviation of achievement scores in post test of GIRLS of experimental and control group

Interpretation of result 1:

The obtained t -value (0.45)of the post test scores is less than the table value(2.21) at the 0.5 level of significance .thus the null hypothesis (Ho.1) is accepted and it can be stated that there is no significant difference between the mathematics achievement of girls taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.

Discussion of the result 1:

The finding of Ho.1 show that mathematics achievement of girls of both the groups in post test is almost equivalent . the reason for this is the researcher taught mathematics to both the groups in an unbiased way. provided reinforcement to both group students on each correct response. some similar finding is of Kathryn (2009)had compared traditional method with interactive board to increase students engagement and achievement in math

class. She concluded that white board is effective tool to teach mathematics but there is no significant difference in the mathematics test scores of students between the traditional method and interactive white board .

Analysis 2.

According to **Ho2:** There is no significant difference between mathematics achievement of boys taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.Ho2 is interpreted on the basis of mean ,standard deviation and t value .

For the verification of Ho.2 . The researcher administered an achievement test in mathematics as pre- test on the boys of experimental group and control group. both the groups boys were academically equal or homogeneous in nature before the experimental treatment was given. The table 3 shows the mean ,standard deviation and t value of the pre test .

Pre - TEST mean score of boys of experimental and control group

Table 3

boys pre test	N	Mean	Sd	Mean difference	T.Value	S OR NS
Experimental	28	2.72	0.88	0.01	0.98	NS
Control group	32	2.71	0.95			

Df 58, los at 0.05 = 2.00 and at 0.01= 2.66

The ‘t’ value is 0.98.of the pre test scores of girls of experimental and control group. This value is statistically not significant at 0.5 level of significance .Further , researcher started the teaching experiment on the samples .boys of control group were taught by traditional class method and boys of experimental group were taught through smart board. after the treatment or teaching session was over boys of both the groups were post tested by the same achievement test of mathematics .the result is mentioned below in table 4:

Post - TEST mean score of boys of experimental and control group

Table 4

Post test	N	Mean	Sd	Mean difference	T.Value	S OR NS
Experimental	28	18.86	2.73	4.18	5.63	S
Control group	32	14.68	3.64			

Df 58 , los at 0.05 = 2.00 and at 0.01= 2.66

The graphical representation of the post test scores is given in the figure 2.

Result of analysis 2: Table no.4 and figure no. 2 show the mean achievement of boys of experimental and control group .the mean values are 18.86 and 14.68 respectively. The t value is 4.18 between post test scores of boys of experimental and control group ,which is statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance with degree of freedom 58.

Interpretation of result 2 :

Table 4 shows that The obtained t value(5.63) is higher than the table value (2.00)at the 0.5 level of significance .thus the null hypothesis (Ho.1) is rejected and it can be stated that there is a significant difference between the mathematics achievement of boys taught by smart classroom teaching and conventional mode of teaching.

Discussion of the result 2 :

The finding of Ho.1 show mean achievement of boys of smart class or experimental group is higher than the control group. This indicate that boys of experimental group have performed better than boys of control group. Thus it may be said that this difference may be due to the experimental treatment given to the boys of experimental group through smart class. This difference reveals that teaching through smart class is more beneficial in gaining in achievement of boys in comparison to conventional teaching method .recently, JaechoonJo, Heuseok Lim (2015) studied on effectiveness of smart classrooms through interaction analysis for 5th grade students. Smart classrooms have more positive effects on education than traditional classroom.

Analysis 3.

According to Ho3:There is no significant difference between achievement of boys and girls taught through smart classroom teaching.

Verification of the hypothesis 3: for the verification of Ho.3 or to attain third main objective the research was to compare the achievement of boys and girls taught through smart classroom teaching in mathematics. Therefore, the means and standard deviation and t value was calculated at pre test stage. Table no.5 show Mean achievement of boys and girls are 2.72 and 2.77 which is equivalent at pre test stage. the t value 0.87 was not significant at 0.5 level with degree of freedom 36.

Table 5

Pre test	N	MEAN	SD	T VALUE	S OR NS
Boys	29	2.72	0.88	0.87	NOT SIGNIFICANT
Girls	9	2.77	0.83		

Further, researcher started the teaching experiment .boys and girls together were taught through smart board. after the treatment or teaching session was over students were post tested by the same achievement test of mathematics .the result is mentioned below of the post test:

TABLE 6

Post test	N	MEAN	SD	T VALUE	S OR NS
Boys	29	18.86	2.73	0.53	NOT SIGNIFICANT
Girls	9	19.55	3.39		

Result of analysis 3 : Table no.6 and figure no. 3 show the mean achievement of post test of boys and girls of experimental group or smart class .the mean values are 18.86 and 19.55 respectively. The t value is 0.53 between post test scores of boys and girls in mathematics this value is statistically not significant at 0.5 level of significance with degree of freedom 36.

Interpretation of result 3 :

The obtained t value is less than the table value at the 0.5 level of significance. Therefore, the Null Hypothesis (H03): There is no significant difference between achievement of boys and girls taught through smart classroom teaching is accepted. This reveals that teaching through smart class is beneficial in gaining in achievement of girls and boys both.

Discussion of the result 3 :

The mean achievement score of girls and boys slightly differ. It may therefore be concluded from the findings that gender has nothing to do with the achievement in mathematics among 9 class students using smart Classroom teaching. Similar findings are : Patricia A. Riska (2010) studied the impact of SMART Board technology on growth in mathematics Achievement of Gifted Learners and concluded that there was no significant growth among gifted students who received instruction using SMART Board Technology. I.Umit Yapiciand Ferit Karakoyun(2016) carried a study on “High school students’ attitudes towards smart board use in Biology classes The students’ attitude scores did not differ statistically with respect to the variables of “gender” and “smart board use time .

Conclusion:

The findings of the present study showed that teaching through smart class is more effective than conventional method of teaching for boys only in gaining achievement in mathematic subject at junior high school level. Also, there was no significant difference in the impact of smart classroom teaching and traditional teaching on the mathematics achievement of girls .therefore, more effort is required to enhance girls achievement in mathematics using different methods or by combining two methods. findings also revealed that there was no significant difference in achievement of boys and girls taught through smart class. This reveals that gender has nothing to do with the achievement in mathematics among 9 class students using smart Classroom teaching.

Educational implications

The educational implication of the present study are as follows:

The findings revealed that smart class is effective in enhancing learning among boys .the teachers may use smart class teaching approach for increasing achievement of the boys in mathematics and other science subjects. Different teaching approach is required to enhance achievement of girls in mathematics. The government schools may make available the basic infrastructure and other facilities required for teaching learning through smart class .The software companies may prepare smart class software at a reasonable price so all students can be reached by its benefits.

Reference:

- Ary,Jacobs and sorenson (2009)Introduction to research in education ,eighth edition ,pp74-76
- Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007)Research Methods in Education ,Sixth edition ,pp62-75
- Best.John.W(2006): And Kahn.James .V.:Research In Education ,Prentice Hall, New Delhi.
- Guilford,J.P(1973). Fundamental Statistics In Psychology And Education,(Eighth Edition)Mcgraw Hill Book Company .
- Saxena,N.R ,Mishra.B.K., Mohanty.R.K.(2012):Fundamental Of Educational Research; R.Lall Book Depot,Meerut,P.273-282
- Bano.N(2016) “Smart Classroom Learning Environment And Performance of First Grade Students –A study .”JSRE Volume 4 Issue 2 February 2016
- SRIVASTAVA .S (2015) “Efficacy of Educomp Smart Class ”International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication ISSN: 2321-8169
- www.google scholar.in
- Lankvelt,Katharyn.Van(2009) :use of interactive whiteboard to increase engagement and achievement in math class,retrieved from <http://jalinskens.wikispaces.com/file/view/katie+final+paper.doc>.
- Patricia A. Riska (2011)the impact of smart board technology on growth in mathematics <http://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1424&context=doctoral&sei-redir=1&referer=http://www.google.co.in/url>

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